

**Placing the ‘Dreaded Eastern Question’ during the
International Crisis: Familiar Concept Shaped by the British Penny
Press in 1875-1878**

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Abstract

This article discusses the presence of the concept of the ‘Eastern Question’ in the British penny press during the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875-1878. Analyzing closely how the authors and editors of Victorian daily newspapers placed the concept in their texts, it articulates the changes in the concept’s meanings throughout the crisis. The article underlines the familiarity of the concept to Victorian newsmakers and its gradual introduction after the crisis started. It also indicates how the changes in articles’ titles shifted the meanings of the concept. Additionally, it asks how the crisis and omnipresent references to the ‘Eastern Question’ influenced the approaches to placing advertisements in the British penny press between 1875–1878, thus contributing to the existing literature dealing with the economy of news. Finally, pointing out how the concept was used, it argues that the newspapers’ authors presented different temporalities for the possible solution of the Eastern Question. Visions of short-term and long-term solutions intertwined, revealing the “heteroglossia,” to use Martic Conboy’s term, often evident in the same newspaper issue. Ultimately, the article defines an international crisis as a crucial point for

the historical concepts as their meanings were significantly debated and transformed in the flourishing media environment.

Keywords: *Great Eastern Crisis, penny press, Eastern question*

Introduction

On 25 March 1878, The Manchester Guardian reported that the ship Eastern Question was ready to deliver cotton from Liverpool to New York.³⁴⁸ On the same day, The Daily News published a telegram from Reuters about the situation in Greece that, according to the text, depended “upon England for an equitable solution of the Eastern Question.”³⁴⁹ Furthermore, The Standard presented the review on the book *Armenia and the Campaign of 1877* with the reviewer's comment on “more and more keen interest in the Eastern Question.”³⁵⁰ It was a single concept, the ‘Eastern Question,’ that united texts dealing with commerce, international relations, and literature.³⁵¹ This concept appeared regularly on the pages of Victorian daily press during the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875-1878, a period of instability in Europe that started from the uprising in Herzegovina and continued until the Treaty of Berlin was signed in July 1878.

Historians of media argue that the second half of the nineteenth century was marked by the development of war correspondence, emergence of new journalism, and general commodification of information in the British Empire.³⁵² Uprisings and warfare presented solid

³⁴⁸ “Clearances of Cotton Ships,” *The Manchester Guardian*, March 25, 1878, 4.

³⁴⁹ “England and Greece,” *The Daily News*, March 25, 1878, 5.

³⁵⁰ “New Books,” *The Standard*, March 25, 1878, 2.

³⁵¹ Throughout this article I approach the ‘Eastern Question’ as a historical concept, whose meanings changed throughout the times and geographies and depended on the usage of individuals, anonymized and speaking in public. Therefore, I consider the concept that appeared a given social realm that helps to understand it more thoroughly, following Reinhart Koselleck and putting this text in contrast to Holly Case’s account on “questions” vividly present in the public sphere of Europe between 1850-1950 (See Reinhart Koselleck, ‘Begriffsgeschichte and Social History’, in *Futures Past: On the Semantics of Historical Time*, transl. Keith Tribe (New York: Columbia University Press, 2004), 75–92; Holly Case, *The Age of Questions or, A First Attempt at an Aggregate History of the Eastern, Social, Woman, American, Jewish, Polish, Bullion, Tuberculosis, and Many Other Questions over the Nineteenth Century, and Beyond* (Princeton & Oxford: Princeton University Press, 2018), 4–6). With that, however, Case’s reference to Foucault in her observations on the circulation of the “questions” that had to be solved, is still essential for the part of the present.

³⁵² See, e.g., Andrew Griffiths, *The New Journalism, the New Imperialism and the Fiction of Empire, 1870–1900* (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2015); Jean. K. Chalaby, *The Invention of Journalism* (New York: Palgrave MacMillan, 1998); Joel H. Wiener, *The Americanization of the British Press, 1830s–1914. Speed in the Age of Transatlantic Journalism* (London: Routledge, 2011); Andrew King, Alexis Easley, John Morton, eds., *The Routledge Handbook to Nineteenth-Century: British Periodicals and Newspapers* (London & New York: Routledge, 2016).

ground for sensations about the barely known Other, the subjects of the Ottoman Empire, to be highlighted. Among others, the concept of the ‘Eastern Question’ appeared as one of the most prominent in these texts. Traditionally, scholars refer to it to interpret the images of decline that the Ottoman Empire experienced between the end of the eighteenth and the beginning of the twentieth century. Historians of diplomacy frequently invoked the ‘Eastern Question’ in order to explain the struggle between the Great Powers for the heritage of the Ottomans and presented it as a relatively stable concept in history in general and during the crisis of 1875-1878 in particular, rarely pointing out the possible changes and variations in its usage.³⁵³ Recently, several scholars have gone beyond the focus on traditional diplomatic history and approached the concept from the perspective of intellectual history and the new political history of the British Empire.³⁵⁴ Although their research clarifies the complex presence of the concept in imperial public discourse, they nevertheless ignore the media aspect of the story.³⁵⁵ Attempts to generalize the attitudes toward the Eastern Question within the empire thus leave the simultaneous circulation of its meanings aside, forming the gap that this article aims to cover.

This article explores the concept of the ‘Eastern Question’ based on its placement on the pages of Victorian daily newspapers in 1875-1878. It focuses on the mass penny press, primarily London-based *The Standard*, *The Daily News*, *The Daily Telegraph*, and the regional *The Manchester Guardian*.³⁵⁶ Articles from *The Morning Post* published in 1875 are also taken into

³⁵³ See John A. R. Marriott, *The Eastern Question; an Historical Study in European Diplomacy*. (Oxford: The Clarendon Press, 1917), 1–3; Robert W. Seton-Watson, *Disraeli, Gladstone and the Eastern Question: a Study in Diplomacy and Party Politics* (New York: W. W. Norton & Company Inc., 1972), ix, 113, 479; Mikhail N. Pokrovskii, *Diplomatia i Voiny Tsarskoj Rossii v XIX Stoletii* (London: Overseas Publications Interchange, 1991), 24, 179, 230; Nina S. Kinyapkina, “Vvedenie,” in *Vostochnyj Vopros vo Vneshnej Politike Rossii: Konets XVIII – Nachalo XX v.*, ed. Nina Stepanovna Kinyapkina (Moskva: «Nauka», 1978), 3–10; Robert Blake, *Disraeli* (New York: St. Martin's Press, 1967), 602–605; Martin Swartz, *The Politics of British Foreign Policy in the Era of Disraeli and Gladstone* (London: The Macmillan Press, 1985), 38–41.

³⁵⁴ Gerald D. Clayton, *Britain and Eastern Question: Missolonghi to Gallipoli* (London: University of London Press, Ltd, 1971), 153; au Aucht Ioni “Fro th Eastern Question to the Death of r Re en ons o idd st i th V torian Period o er t i 8 no. 1 (2001 5–24 Milos Ko d New York: Oxford ive it Pr s, 1 vi i Je e beralism and the Balkans, c. 18 –1 5” D is , iv si o Lo on 20 36.

³⁵⁵ A dissertation by Leslie Schumac s, perhaps, the exception in this case. Presenting the relations between British politics, public discourse and diplomacy during the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875-1878, he pays attention to the role of the media in sharing information about the Eastern Question at the time. With that, however, he does not go beyond the fixed definition of the Eastern question as a phenomenon connected with the decline of the Ottoman Empire. See Leslie R. Schumacher, “A «Lasting Solution»: the Eastern Question and British Imperialism, 1875–1878” (PhD diss. The University of Minnesota, 2012), vi–vii, 1–3.

³⁵⁶ I worked with the digital copies of the newspapers provided by The British Newspaper Archive (<https://www.britishnewspaperarchive.co.uk/>). The issues of *The Standard* from July 1, 1876, to December 31, 1876 are absent in the archive, so I was not able to analyze them. The issues of *The Manchester Guardian* were taken from Newspapers.com digital archive.

consideration to clarify the circulation of the concept before and at the beginning of the crisis.³⁵⁷ Using online tools to work with the newspapers, I created a database for the concept's appearance in each of the newspapers, which I later used for both quantitative and qualitative analysis.³⁵⁸

My approach to the meanings of the 'Eastern Question' was informed by Reinhart Koselleck's paradigm of "futures past" and Boris Maslov and Yury Kagarlitskiy's methodological observations about individual interpretations of the concepts, which provided useful background to conceptual history.³⁵⁹ Reflecting on the categories of the "space of experience" and "horizon of expectations" as useful for historical analysis, Koselleck highlights the importance of temporalization of historical concepts and their changing character across time and argues for using analytical categories that were not articulated in the language in the past to understand historical circumstances.³⁶⁰ These categories are essential as "they provide guidance to concrete agencies in the course of social or political movement."³⁶¹ In this article, I incorporate both categories pointed out by Koselleck to underline the changes in the language Victorian daily newspapers authors applied between 1875 and 1878. The changes often occur when there is a transformation in the concepts that have a constructive role within discourses they circulate in, as Maslov and Kagarlitskiy point out.³⁶² For them, however, the discourses are first and foremost political, while this article proposes to look at the media *per se* and its role in shaping the meanings of the concept of the 'Eastern Question' during the four years of the crisis, which allows to look at the usage of the concept on a day-to-day basis. To contextualize that usage, I

³⁵⁷ *The Standard* and *The Morning Post* were conservative newspapers, while *The Daily News* remained the only prominent newspaper that supported Liberal party after the elections in 1874. *The Daily Telegraph* shifted to Conservatives during the Great Eastern Crisis. *The Manchester Guardian* became an important regional newspaper thanks to telegraph. It also mostly leaned to the thoughts of Liberal politicians (see Bourne H. R. Fox, *English Newspapers: Chapters in the History of Journalism. Volume 2* (New York: Russell & Russell, 1966), 334-335, Wiener, *The Americanization of the British Press*, 103).

³⁵⁸ To identify the concept's presence, I used online tools offered by the British Newspaper Archive and Newspapers.com. Starting with searching the keyword "The Eastern Question," I went manually through every mention of the word combination or its alterations in 1875-1878. This inquiry resulted in several tables featuring the date the concept was mentioned, the form the concept had, the place where it was put (both page and column), and the context of its appearance.

³⁵⁹ Reinhart Koselleck, *Futures Past: On the Semantics of Historical Time*, transl. Keith Tribe (New York: Columbia University Press, 2004); Boris Maslov and Yury Kagarlitskiy, "Mezhdu Frege i Fuko: Metodologicheskie Osnovy Istoricheskoy Semantiki," in *Poniatiiia, Idei, Konstruktsii*, ed. Yury Kagarlitskiy, Dmitrii Kalugin, and Boris Maslov (Moskva: Novoe Literaturnoe Obozrenie, 2019), 9-38.

³⁶⁰ Reinhart Koselleck, "«Space of Experience» and «Horizon of Expectation»: Two Historical Categories," in *Futures Past*, 255.

³⁶¹ Koselleck, "«Space of Experience»," 258.

³⁶² Maslov and Kagarlitskiy, "Mezhdu Frege i Fuko," 31-34.

also paid attention to the approaches to study Victorian journalism and print culture through the lens of sociolinguistics proposed by Lyn Pykett and Martin Conboy.³⁶³ In particular, Conboy proposes to use the concept of ‘heteroglossia’ to explain the circulation of information in the Victorian press, arguing that newspaper texts presented a dialogic space that contested the dominant social-linguistic norms.³⁶⁴ This notion was helpful for the analysis of the variability of meanings connected to the concept of the Eastern Question. At the same time, the authors’ anonymity did not allow me to identify all the writers of the texts, which is why I focus on other markers that may show the multiplicity of interpretations.³⁶⁵

Already the first glance at the appearance of the ‘Eastern Question’ reveals its presence in editorial articles, columns with international and commercial news, and sections on advertisement, which made its presence ubiquitous in the daily press between 1875-1878 (See Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4). Yet, different authors and editors granted the concept with multiple meanings, which were based on their choices of overall narratives for articles or specific connotations within a given piece of a text. That dynamic encourages one to look closer at where and how the concept appeared when the crisis that started in a small vilayet of the Ottoman Empire resonated within the European continent and beyond. To trace these appearances, I considered every instance when the concept of the Eastern Question was used, in one form or another, within the context of each of the newspapers, interpreting the newspaper as text, whose editors might have decided to combine different opinions on the same page.³⁶⁶

Analyzing how the concept was placed in day-to-day issues of five dailies, this article underlines the international crisis as a crucial point for the transformation of the meaning of the historical concept. First, it presents a variety of formulations the authors of the penny press applied to introduce the ‘Eastern Question’ to their readers. It then presents the meanings the concept was given amidst the unfolding events in the Balkans and the attempts to influence those events by the Great Powers, and pays attention to the sections of the newspapers where the concept appeared. Finally, addressing the issue of the solutions of the ‘Eastern Question’ offered

³⁶³ Lyn Pykett, “Reading the Periodical Press: Text and Context,” *Investigating Victorian Journalism*, ed. Laurel Brake, Aled Jones, Lionel Madden (London: Macmillan Press, 1990), 3-18; Martin Conboy, *The Language of Newspapers: Socio-Historical Perspectives* (New York: Continuum International Publishing Group, 2010), 1–11, 98–99.

³⁶⁴ Conboy, *The Language of Newspapers*, 5–6.

³⁶⁵ On anonymity in Victorian newspapers see Alberto Gabriele, *Reading Popular Culture in Victorian Print: Belgravia and Sensationalism* (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009), 69–75.

³⁶⁶ In this article, I consider separate opinions that either appeared as independent texts or were inserted as quotes together to highlight the diversity of the media discourse that influenced the meaning of the given concept.

in the newspapers, this article highlights different temporalities imagined by the authors who had to deal with the unpredictable nature of the ‘dreaded Eastern Question.’³⁶⁷

The Eastern Question: forms and formulations

It would not be hard to trace the resemblance between the classic legend of the Hydra's head and the conditions of Turkey in Europe [...] For the last few months, the minds of European diplomats have been perturbed by the complications arising out of the pretensions of the Danube Principalities to conclude treaties of commerce directly with the foreign Powers; and now, when that moot point has been settled more or less satisfactory, the irrepressible Eastern question recurs in the shape of a feud between Montenegro and Turkey.³⁶⁸

These words opened the editorial published in *The Daily Telegraph* on 21 January 1875. Half a year later, the new recursion of the Eastern Question took place after the uprising in Herzegovina started, with the deserved attention from the British press. The information flows that brought the news from the Balkans, however, were unstable, and so was the number and the nature of references to the concept.³⁶⁹ Facing the need to deal with the news from the ‘East,’ imagined and presented by the newspaper contributors, the penny press revealed a variety of approaches and forms its authors adopted to talk about the supposedly familiar concept.

The number of references to the ‘Eastern Question’ changed from the beginning of the crisis. After twenty mentions of the concept in *The Daily Telegraph* in January 1875, when the tensions between Montenegro and the Ottoman Empire were apparent, the concept disappeared from the pages of the newspaper from May to October, and the new increase in the numbers

³⁶⁷ “France.,” *The Standard*, August 23, 1875, 6.

³⁶⁸ “London, Thursday, January 21.,” *The Daily Telegraph*. January 21, 1875, 4.

³⁶⁹ I borrow the concept of “flows” from Stuart Alexander Rockefeller who presents it as “agentless movement with no starting point and no telos” (see Stuart Alexander Rockefeller, “Flow,” *Current Anthropology* 52, no. 4 (August 2011): 558). Although the news always were created by someone, thus were not “agentless,” the acceleration of information amidst the crisis made it difficult to distinguish separate news items from the general mass of notes, even though the first might have appeared in defined articles. As for the numbers, in his dissertation, Leslie Schumacher points out that the leading newspapers had several hundred articles with the title “The Eastern Question” during the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875-1878 but does not mention when and how these headlines appeared (Schumacher, “A «Lasting Solution», 169).

happened only in November.³⁷⁰ The Eastern Question was used constantly in 1876 (the total number of mentions was 302). In 1877, there were 256 mentions of the concept while the first nine months of 1878 brought 307 mentions (Figure 1). These tendencies seem to correlate with the general development of events in the Balkans at the time. The uprising in Herzegovina and later Bosnia in summer of 1875 brought back the reference to the term. Then, in spring 1876, a rebellion also happened in Bulgaria, and the Ottoman Empire used the *başibozuk*, the irregular troops, in order to put it down. Their violent actions against the civilian Bulgarian population attracted much attention in the British Empire due to the campaign against the government's alleged support for the Ottoman Empire led by the former prime-minister William Gladstone that started after his pamphlet *Bulgarian Atrocities and the Question of the East* was published in September 1876.³⁷¹ Finally, 1877-1878 were the years of the Russo-Ottoman war and the following peaceful negotiations that were also urgent events for the British public.

However, the other daily newspapers demonstrated a different dynamic in 1875. Only 22 mentions of the concept appear in *The Standard*, 19 in *The Daily News*, and 34 in *The Manchester Guardian* during January-September 1875. The number increased sharply in *The Standard* during the following month, while the rise in numbers was more moderate in the other two newspapers. The 'Eastern Question' started appearing regularly in all three from April 1876 onwards. Thus, the authors of the articles in *The Standard*, *The Daily News*, and *The Manchester Guardian* were not interested in using the concept at the beginning of the Great Eastern Crisis, and it only received much attention starting with the Bulgarian uprising in 1876 (Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4).

The differences in the numbers of mentions may be explained by the fact that back in January 1875, *The Daily Telegraph* introduced a separate column under the title "The Eastern Question" in the part "General Foreign News," where the telegrams from abroad were regularly published.³⁷² From mid-January 1875, 'The Eastern Question' had become a separate column

³⁷⁰ The editorial's note quoted at the start of this section refers directly to this tension. Montenegro gained a semi-independent status after winning a conflict with the Ottoman Empire in 1858 but her independence was not formally recognized until the Congress of Berlin in 1878. For a brief overview of the Ottoman-Montenegrin relations see e.g., Sumner, *Russia and the Balkans*, 132–134.

³⁷¹ William E. Gladstone, *Bulgarian Horrors and the Question of the East* (New York and Montreal: Lovell, Adam, Wesson and Company, 1876).

³⁷² See "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 2, 1875, 3; "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 6, 1875, 3; "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 12, 1875, 3.

without direct connection with other news from abroad.³⁷³ The telegrams about the events in the Balkans as well as international reactions to these events were reported by special correspondents from European capitals or Reuters.³⁷⁴ This column seems to be an editor's decision to present the events from the East within the defined conceptual frame put in the title 'The Eastern Question.'³⁷⁵ At the same, neither of the collection of telegrams explained the meanings of this Eastern Question and, therefore, the authors presumed that the readers were familiar with the concept.³⁷⁶

Implicit presumption of the familiarity with the concept still left the newspapers contributors with necessity to face the uncertainties of the unfolding international crisis.³⁷⁷ Thus, the notion that the phases of the Eastern Question could change during a single day, asserted by liberal politician William Adam in January 1876, made the situation even more unstable and complicated.³⁷⁸ It uncovers the tendency toward the temporalization of concepts, typical for the modern era.³⁷⁹ The modern concepts usually described particular processes rather than static phenomena, and the Eastern Question, based on Adam's observations, marked one of such processes, with its referent being mostly outside, either at the theatre of uprising or somewhere within the channels of diplomatic communication.

³⁷³ "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 15, 1875, 3; "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 18, 1875, 3.

³⁷⁴ After the telegraph was nationalized in 1868, the news market in the British Empire also changed. In 1870, the Association of Provincial Newspapers signed an agreement with Reuters about the reduced price for the news from abroad in exchange for the regional news free of charge. London Newspapers *The Daily Telegraph*, *The Standard*, and *The Daily News* did not join the agreement, so the tariff for the foreign news was high. Thus, it was cheaper for them to have special correspondents in European capitals than to receive all the information from the news agency. See Jonathan Silberstein-Loeb, "The Structure of the News Market in Britain, 1870-1914," *The Business History Review* 83, no. 4 (2009): 767-775). At the same time, all three newspapers also continued to purchase information from Reuters.

³⁷⁵ Niklas Luhmann defined the editorial presentation of information as "coding." For him, every journal or newspaper issue contained particular code formed by the editors. Thus, the code transferred the foundations of editorial politics (See Niklas Luhmann, *The Reality of Mass-Media*, transl. Kate Cross (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2000), 15-20).

³⁷⁶ In this context I refer to the ideal type of a reader who, as Martin Conboy points out, usually is constructed within the language of newspapers and, in fact, participates in the creation of senses by the newspaper (Martin Conboy, *The Language of Newspapers*, 3).

³⁷⁷ The interpretations of the events in the Ottoman Empire as the "crisis" first appeared in the penny press in mid-autumn 1875, three months after the start of the uprising in Bosnia (see, e.g., "London, Saturday, October 9, 1875.," *The Morning Post*, October 9, 1875, 4; "The Eastern Question.," *The Standard*, November 11, 1875, 5 "The Turkish Crisis," *The Daily Telegraph*, November 18, 5). The notion of the crisis, in this context, could also have different meaning, as a moment of decision as well as the prolonged stage of uncertainty, but to deal with that would require a separate article (on crisis, see Reinhart Koselleck and Michaela W. Richter, "Crisis," *Journal of the History of Ideas* 67, no. 2 (2006): 357-400).

³⁷⁸ "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 15, 1877, 2.

³⁷⁹ Kagarlitskiĭ and Maslov, "Between Frege and Foucault, 29.

The form in which the concept was placed in the penny press was also unstable because of intended sensationalization.³⁸⁰ Throughout the crisis, the formulations that marked the concept always contained the adjective *Eastern* (sometimes *Oriental*), but the last part seemed to be a matter of choice. Along with the “Eastern Question,” the editors and contributors of all major daily newspapers also used a wide variety of expressions to sensationalize their texts: “Eastern affairs,” “Eastern matters,” “Eastern situation,” “Eastern controversy,” “Eastern complication(s),” “Eastern difficulty(ies),” “Eastern concert,” “Eastern problem,” “Eastern quarrel,” “Eastern struggle,” “Eastern troubles,” “Eastern menace,” “Eastern mess,” “Eastern deadlock,” “Eastern tragedy,” “Eastern falsetto,” “the Eastern imbroglio,” “the Eastern chaos” and “the Eastern drama.” Different forms made the whole message sound more sensational, while the concept’s meanings remained preserved.

The concept’s form was also profoundly shaped by newspapers’ special correspondents.³⁸¹ In 1875, telegrams with information about the affairs in South-Eastern Europe often contained emotional metaphors like “anxious of reopening,” “reopen of the terrible Eastern Question,” “sullen menace,” and “terrible eventuality.”³⁸² On the one hand, these expressions could mark the concerns expressed by the special correspondents. On the other hand, all of them contained the elements of sensationalism, as explained by Norman Fairclough.³⁸³ Together with emotional formulations of the concept per se, they could make the message of the article more vivid. Thus, regardless of the type of the text, the Eastern Question presented a good ground for the writers’ creativity that allowed to highlight the overly present anxieties about the future, which I will discuss later in this article.

What the sensational frame of the news about the Eastern Question aimed at was to encourage the readers’ interest in the still little-known East. In the collection of news about the ongoing events in the British Empire, published in *The Daily Telegraph* on 22 December 1877, the notion about the development of “this infernal Eastern tragedy” appeared. Later in the text an

³⁸⁰ On the intentional sensationalization of news, see Chalaby, *The Invention of Journalism*, 97–98.

³⁸¹ On the role of special correspondents in the 1870s, see Andrew Griffiths *The New Journalism*, 26–27, Wiener, *The Americanization of the British Press*, 96.

³⁸² “Russia and the East,” *The Daily Telegraph*, February 1, 1875, 5; “The study of various telegrams...” *The Manchester Guardian*, September 14, 1875, 5; “We are told that...” *The Daily Telegraph*, January 22, 1875, 5; “France,” *The Standard*, August 31, 1875, 5.

³⁸³ Fairclough points out that the sensationalist texts produce the sense of alarm, stressed by particular words (e.g. deadly, dangerous or toxic). The authors of these texts play the role of entertainers whose works are “simultaneously representing, setting up identities, and setting up relations” (see Norman Fairclough, *Media Discourse* (London: Arnold, 1995), 4–5).

anonymous author reflected on the Russo-Ottoman war and the difficulties that the war presented before the British government.³⁸⁴ A similar approach of making the news more sensitive appeared in the editorial article published in *The Standard* on 24 December. Focusing on Germany's involvement in the attempts to solve the conflict in the East, the author presumed that Germans hardly could enjoy their role in the “Eastern drama.”³⁸⁵ Sensational news was typical for capital and provincial newspapers in the 1870s. Edward Lewi, the owner of *The Daily Telegraph*, was a pioneer when he made the principle of human interest a cornerstone of the newspaper from the very beginning that correlated with the ideas of New Journalism that emerged at the time.³⁸⁶ However, as Martin Conboy claims, additional accents that were attached to the important news became quite ordinary in the 1870s.³⁸⁷ Thus, the editorial decisions to make information sound more appealing led to the shape of the concept, creatively adapted in the press, which detached it from the context of politics where it originated.³⁸⁸

The variety of possible formulations coexisted with the idea that multiple Eastern questions could exist amidst the crisis. In summer 1875, *The Morning Post* published an article whose author pointed out that “all the Eastern Questions are less interesting to France than to England.”³⁸⁹ By referring to the Eastern questions, he mentioned Constantinople as the key to the Mediterranean, the loans for the Ottoman empire, Egypt and the Suez Canal. The last two ‘questions’ represented a spatial dimension of the issue that was even more vivid with the case of Syria and Levant. Some observers included these territories in the Eastern Question, while others put it aside.³⁹⁰ Therefore, the authors defined the spatial marks of the concept differently, sometimes presenting them as related to several eastern questions. What then constituted those “questions”?

³⁸⁴ “«Fair Play» writes...,” *The Daily Telegraph*, December 22, 1877, 3.

³⁸⁵ “That in official...,” *The Standard*, December 24, 4.

³⁸⁶ Jean K. Chalaby, *The Invention of Journalism*, 147–155.

³⁸⁷ Martin Conboy, *The Language of Newspapers*, 91–92.

³⁸⁸ On the origins of the Eastern Question, *The Eastern Question*.

³⁸⁹ “France.,” *The Morning Post*, June 23, 1875, 6.

³⁹⁰ “Money Market.,” *The Daily Telegraph*, June 9, 1876, 2; “A day like New Year's-day...,” *The Standard*, January 1, 1877, 4; “England and the East.,” *The Standard*, January 1, 1878, 3; “We have reason...,” *The Daily Telegraph*, August 25, 1875, 4.

Attempting a Definition: What Was the ‘Eastern Question’?

An anonymous article published in *The Standard* on 1 June 1878, a couple of weeks before the Congress of Berlin started, presents one of the clearest examples of the ambiguities germane to the discussions around the ‘Eastern Question.’ Reflecting on the issues connected to the definition of the question, the author pointed out that it was indeed difficult to find a single explanation for it:

At one time, even Englishmen persuaded themselves that it was only a Bulgarian question. Russia, in the levity of ambitious impulses, conceived that it was only a question between herself and Turkey. These and other kindred mistakes are now recognised as such by the slowest intelligences. We have before us a Christian question, a Mahometan question, a Slav question, a Hungarian question, an Austro-Hungarian question, a Servian question, a Montenegrin question, a Roumanian question, a Greek question, an Italian question, a Europo-Turkish question, a Turco-Asiatic question, a British Empire question. It is enough to take away one's breath. Yet we have by no means exhausted the list of questions which are embraced in those brief and familiar words, the Eastern Question. *We have named only the most conspicuous and most urgent.*³⁹¹ (emphasis added)

The variety of the components that, in the author’s opinion, constituted the Eastern Question, was only one attempt to reflect on the undefined concept. At the peak of Bulgarian agitation, an anonymous author concluded that people in the British Empire might “know really as much now about the Eastern Question as many professional diplomats.”³⁹² This knowledge was regularly presented to a wider public but simultaneously was atomized by the daily press. Yet there were three prominent themes raised by the authors when they referred to the concept, namely morality and religion, the Balkans, and domestic politics.

Historians have shown that the religious component was an important part of the Eastern Question throughout the nineteenth century.³⁹³ The idea of struggle between the Christians and

³⁹¹ “Although no statement...,” *The Standard*, June 1, 1878, 4.

³⁹² “Events must decide...,” *The Daily Telegraph*. 1876. September 28, 4.

³⁹³ See., e.g, Marriott, *The Eastern Question*; Milos Ković, “Disraeli’s Orientalism Reconsidered,” *Serbian Political Thought*, no. 1 (2016): 5-14; Zoran Grijak, “Croatian – British views of the Eastern Question: The

Muslims was easily implemented into the history and the present of the Eastern Question within Victorian intellectual culture. Still, the authors of daily newspapers presented ambiguous views on the concept's connection with religion. Some of them pointed out that the Eastern Question was a religious question, while the Russian Empire transformed it into a political one.³⁹⁴ Others mentioned directly that the question did have a religious component.³⁹⁵ In particular, a priest Canon Liddon mentioned that it was not a question of religion, but rather a question of humanity. He referred to the oppression that the population of the European part of the Ottoman empire experienced from "one of the most barbarous despotisms that ever oppressed any portion of the human race."³⁹⁶ Such a humanitarian perspective was not exclusive.³⁹⁷ On 27 November 1876, *The Daily Telegraph* published an article whose author argued that the Eastern Question was a question of "response of Europe, general prosperity, and Christian civilization."³⁹⁸ Leslie Schumacher defines similar interpretations as a new version of the Eastern Question that emerged as a reaction from the British population to the 'Bulgarian atrocities' that occurred in spring and summer 1876.³⁹⁹ However, its 'new version' was, in fact, one of many possible interpretations of the concept that emerged between 1875 and 1878. The discussion about the humanitarian aspect of the question indeed appeared after the news from Bulgaria reached the British Empire and provoked the 'Bulgarian agitation.' Yet, within the newspapers' texts it was only an addition to the previous interpretations of the connections between morality, religion and the concept itself.

At the same time, the view on the Eastern Question as an issue of the ongoing disturbances in the Balkans appeared regularly in all daily newspapers throughout the crisis. In general, the greatest number of mentions of the concept was connected to this region, but naturally no consensus was established between the authors. *The Standard's* editors revealed their complex

correspondence of William Ewart Gladstone and Josip Juraj Strossmayer (1876-1882)." *Review of Croatian History* V, br. 1 (2009): 47–84.

³⁹⁴ "The lamentable bloodshed..." *The Standard*, August 20, 1878, 4; "As soon as the Russian troops..." *The Standard*, August 21, 1878, 4. See also "Old Catholic Conference..." *The Daily Telegraph*, August 14, 1875, 5.

³⁹⁵ "Nothing more untoward..." *The Daily Telegraph*, May 9, 1876, 5.

³⁹⁶ "Canon Liddon on the Eastern Question..." *The Standard*, February 2, 1877, 6.

³⁹⁷ The discourses of 'humanitarianism' were prominent in the British Empire in the second half of the nineteenth century. See Abigail Green, "Humanitarianism in Nineteenth-Century Context: Religious, Gendered, National," *The Historical Journal*, Vol. 57, No. 4 (December 2014): 1157–1175; Abigail Green, "The British Empire and the Jews: An Imperialism of Human Rights?," *Past & Present* 199, Issue 1 (May 2008): 175–205; Michelle Tusan, *Smyrna's Ashes: Humanitarianism, Genocide, and the Birth of the Middle East* (Berkeley and Los Angeles, CA: University of California Press, 2012).

³⁹⁸ "If the special telegram..." *The Daily Telegraph*, November 27, 1876, 4.

³⁹⁹ Leslie R. Schumacher, "A «Lasting Solution»," 98–99.

views in the column “The Eastern Question” that was introduced in autumn 1875. For instance, the telegram from Paris published in the column on 10 November 1875, contained reports about the attempts to cope with the situation in the Balkans made by the League of the Three Emperors.⁴⁰⁰ In this case, the Eastern Question was presented as the question of relation between the Great Powers and the Ottoman Empire and as the direction of those powers’ foreign policy. Therefore, the meanings of the concept could be changed depending on the editors' arrangement of the texts that they decided to publish.

Other authors also had a flexible approach to interpreting the Eastern Question in relation to the Balkans. In April 1875, *The Standard* published an article about the increased tensions between the Ottoman Empire and Serbia where the author argued that the Eastern Question became a Serbian question.⁴⁰¹ In a different article two years later, the Eastern Question was connected with the “new Bulgarian Question.”⁴⁰² The article’s author defined the presence of the Ottomans in Europe as only one among many factors that influenced an unstable situation in the Balkans and pointed out that the “Hellenic factor” was also a part of the Eastern Question.⁴⁰³ He claimed that Greeks had their interests and put themselves against Turks and Bulgarians that also caused the tensions on the peninsula.⁴⁰⁴ Similar thoughts about Greeks and Greece as a part of or an independent side in the Eastern Question also appeared on the pages of the daily press.⁴⁰⁵ Additionally, after the Congress of Berlin opened, *The Standard* published an article titled “The Roumanian Question.” The author identified a new phase of the Eastern Question related to the question of the future fate of Bessarabia, for which the Russian Empire expressed its claims.⁴⁰⁶ Although other authors mentioned Romania in the context of the question earlier, it was the first time in four years when the country was presented as an independent part in relation to it.⁴⁰⁷

⁴⁰⁰ “Paris, Tuesday Evening,” *The Standard*, November 10, 1875, 5.

⁴⁰¹ “Russia,” *The Standard*, April 19, 1875, 6.

⁴⁰² “What has been euphemistically...,” *The Standard*, January 6, 1877, 4.

⁴⁰³ The argument about the bad governance of the Ottomans as an important factor of the Eastern Question was also mentioned by other contributors (See e.g. “London, Tuesday, Oct. 30.,” *The Daily News*, October 30, 1877, 4; “Mr. W. E. Forster, M. P. on the War,” *The Manchester Guardian*. January 7, 1878, 6).

⁴⁰⁴ “What has been euphemistically...,” 4.

⁴⁰⁵ “Affairs at Constantinople,” *The Daily News*, October 4, 1876, 6; “The Turks have suffered...,” *The Standard*, October 19, 1877, 4; “Greece and Greeks,” *The Daily News*, December 11, 1877, 7; Zante, “Greece and the Eastern Question,” *The Manchester Guardian*, February 18, 1878, 6.; “Greece and Turkey,” *The Daily Telegraph*, August 26, 1878, 5.

⁴⁰⁶ “The Roumanian Question,” *The Standard*, Ju 17, 1878, 6.

⁴⁰⁷ Contin the a is wa v be 1877 n n o i um t s W y p e c s r Gua ian March 15, 1878, 8; “Russia and Ro ania.” *e Manches* 78, 7).

Thus, the concept was like a mosaic put within the frame of the imagined Balkans, where the were added and taken out depending on the reactions to the changing situation in the region.

The reactive nature of the changes in the meanings was also visible in the coverage of the Balkan politics of the Great Powers. The author of an article published in *The Standard* on February 27, 1877, pointed out that two Eastern Questions existed simultaneously – “pure Turkish question and Russo-Turkish question.”⁴⁰⁸ He thus distinguished the internal problems of the Ottoman Empire from its relations with the Russian Empire, while both were seen as a part of the “European question” and were related to the interests of other European powers. The Paris correspondent of *The Standard* earlier presented a similar opinion arguing that from the point of *raison d'etat*, the Eastern Question was, in fact, the “Western question.”⁴⁰⁹ In this case, European powers preserved the ties with the Balkans, a main stage of the Eastern Question, but were seen as external actors in relation to the question itself.

The envisioned “civilizing mission” of the Europeans made them a part of the Eastern Question on the pages of Victorian dailies. In the report about the Liberal party meeting in St. James Hall in London published in *The Daily Telegraph* on 10 October 1876, the author quoted Sir James Stansfeld, M.P., who argued that “the Eastern Question was ... a European question – a question involving grave responsibility upon the part of Europe.”⁴¹⁰ Later Stansfeld appealed to the thesis about the civilizing mission Europeans had to bring to the East, and that was their visible relation to the Eastern Question. A similar observation was made by a French correspondent of *The Daily News* who reported on 26 November 1876, about his talks with Paris inhabitants on the Eastern Question. Commenting on the ongoing Serbo-Ottoman war, his companions pointed out that France had to send its troops to the Balkans because “Servians will delight in an army of occupation. We shall civilize them, teach them to dance and talk scandal.”⁴¹¹ From their perspective, “[t]his will be the true solution of the Eastern question.”⁴¹² Presented in an engaging tone, the article diluted the ongoing debate around “Bulgarian atrocities” with a less serious but nevertheless appealing civilizing message.

The imagined stage of the Eastern drama could also vary from time to time. On September 30, 1878, *The Standard* reprinted a fragment of an article published in the Russian newspaper

⁴⁰⁸ “During the long, difficult, February 27, 1877, 4.

⁴⁰⁹ “France.,” *The Standard*, August 31, 1875, 5.

⁴¹⁰ “Meeting in St. James’s Hall.,” *The Daily Telegraph*, October 10, 1876, 3.

⁴¹¹ “Coffee-House Bubble.,” *The Daily News*, November 24, 1876, 6.

⁴¹² “Coffee-House Bubble.,” 6.

The Exchange News, in which the author argued that the simplest definition of the Eastern Question was the struggle between Russia and England, and the competition between the empires for the Eastern territories was highlighted. However, in this case, the East was presented not by the Balkans, but by Afghanistan and India.⁴¹³ Such a notion shows that not all the messages presented in the Victorian daily press limited the Eastern Question to South-Eastern Europe, and the imagined boundaries of the question could be flexibly expanded.

Yet, it was the domestic politics that shaped the meaning of the Eastern Question most drastically during the Great Eastern Crisis. On 13 December 1876, *The Daily Telegraph* published an article under the title, “The Eastern Question” where the dinner hosted by the Earl of Mount Edgcumbe was described.⁴¹⁴ Among other remarks an anonymous correspondent paid attention to the words of conservative politician Messis Lopes who was dissatisfied with the attempts to transform the Eastern Question to the “party question.”⁴¹⁵ Lopes believed in the clear motives of Disraeli's government to obtain freedom for the Balkan Christians and was concerned with the attempts of Liberal politicians to discredit the foreign policy of the British Empire.⁴¹⁶ Before the “Bulgarian agitation” led by William Gladstone started in autumn 1876, there was no single mention of the connection between the Eastern Question and domestic party affairs. The huge public campaign against the government's neutrality toward the Ottoman empire shifted the perception sharply.

The shift was felt not only during the gatherings of politicians. On 13 January 1878, *The Standard* published a letter signed as Traveler, who shared his experience about the situation in Canada. He argued that at the time when the people in England “are bringing the Eastern question down to the level of party issues, the Canadians look at it only in its bearing upon national, or rather Imperial interests.”⁴¹⁷ In September 1878, conservative politician Philip Wroughton stated that “unfortunately it [the Eastern Question] had been made a party question.”⁴¹⁸ Even two years after the Bulgarian agitation, the issue of internal party relations was brought into focus.

⁴¹³ “The Indian Crisis,” *The Standard*, September 30, 1878, 5.

⁴¹⁴ Mentioned as Mount Edgcumbe in the original text.

⁴¹⁵ “The Eastern Question,” *The Daily Telegraph*, December 4, 1876, 3. Lopes used the phrase ‘the Eastern Affairs,’ which was framed by the newspaper author as a synonym of the ‘Eastern Question.’

⁴¹⁶ “The Eastern Question,” *The Daily Telegraph*, December 1876, 3.

⁴¹⁷ “Canadian Loyalty,” *The Standard*, January 1, 1877, 3.

⁴¹⁸ “Members of the constituents,” *The Standard*, September 78,

The more significant sign of the changes in the meanings of the Eastern Question is related to the reappearance of the regular column “The Eastern Question” on the pages of *The Daily Telegraph* on 9 September 1876. The column did not contain any telegrams from abroad this time. Instead, it consisted of several articles about the discussions related to the Bulgarian “atrocities” and the recently published pamphlet by William Gladstone.⁴¹⁹ The events in South-Eastern Europe were not directly mentioned in any of the articles. Rather the Eastern Question marked a discussion about the events that had already happened. In the following months, the editors regularly published the information regarding the public gatherings and speeches, letters from different people, short telegrams from the regions of the kingdom in the column.⁴²⁰ Similar columns were also published in *The Daily News* on 9 September and in *The Manchester Guardian* on 7 October.⁴²¹ The authors of these columns almost completely ignored the situation in the East at that time, leaving them to other contributors. For instance, in the issue published in *The Daily Telegraph* on October 6, the editors put two letters, three short notes, long stories about a speech by a liberal politician, William Forster, and a gathering in Hackney (a part of London), and three telegrams about gatherings in Birkenhead, Edinburg, and Sheffield.⁴²² Only one short note among them contained a direct reaction on the ongoing events in South-Eastern Europe, while all other texts included reflections on the “atrocities” in Bulgaria that had happened several months before.⁴²³ The accusation of Disraeli's government, put together with the responses from the members of Conservative party, and the appeal to the “atrocities,” was seen as more important to underline. Conservative politicians also accused Liberals of undermining the foreign policy of the British Empire but did not always deny the crimes against the Bulgarian population.⁴²⁴

The reflections published in the column uncovered a new meaning of the ‘Eastern Question’ or its “new version,” to use the term proposed by Leslie Schumacher.⁴²⁵ The concept

⁴¹⁹ E t Que io he *Daily Telegraph*, Sept b 9, he ut e B t Empire were also sometime inc ded in e l e . «The Daily Telegraph.»,” *The Daily Tel ra* , pt be 9, 87 3

⁴²⁰ O Fe r 22, 1877, the column “The Eastern Questi egraph for the last time. Among other articles, the editor also included a speech delivered by Marquis Salisbury who had recently come back from the Constantinople Conference (“Speech of Lord Salisbury.”,” *The Daily Telegraph*, February 22, 1877, 3).

⁴²¹ “The Eastern Question.”,” *The Daily News*, September 9, 1876, 3; “The Eastern Question.”,” *The Manchester Guardian*, October 7, 1876, 8.

⁴²² “The Eastern Question.”,” *The Daily Telegraph*, October 6, 1876, 3.

⁴²³ “The Eastern Question.”,” *The Daily Telegraph*, October 6, 1876, 3.

⁴²⁴ P. J. Durrans, “A Two-Edged Sword: The Liberal Attack on Disraelian Imperialism,” *The Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History* 10, no. 3 (1982): 264–277.

⁴²⁵ Leslie R. Schumacher, “A «Lasting Solution»,” 98–99.

was no longer directly connected to the “East,” but rather circulated in the context of internal British affairs, with headlines appearing across the daily press. (see Figure 5) The discussions about the Eastern Question thus became one of the concept’s referents, to which Victorian media directly contributed. Since summer 1875, by mentioning the concept in the texts about local struggles in the imagined East or international struggles related to the imagined East, they had made the Eastern Question omnipresent for their readers. This time, by placing the concept in the headlines of the columns dealing with day-to-day domestic affairs, the editors of the penny press explicitly domesticated it.

Domestication only added to the controversies about the future of the “pending dilemma.”⁴²⁶ While Bulgarian agitation caused the wave of the public meetings and acute discussions about Disraeli’s foreign policy, the waves of Ottoman attacks put the Serbian and Montenegrin troops in a very uneasy position, and only the intervention of the Russian Empire prevented two principalities from the collapse.⁴²⁷ In December 1876, Marquis Salisbury departed to Stambul to participate in the conference that was supposed to deal with the Eastern Question. The conference did not bring any visible results, and its failure only deepened the crisis, which culminated with the Russo-Ottoman war starting in April 1877 with subsequent attempt to solve the Eastern Question at the Congress of Berlin a year later. The next section of the article will bring the visions on its future that appeared in the newspapers whose editors and authors had to deal with these developments daily, when the prospects of the events were uneven, and the same information could equally provoke the glimpses of hope or prolonged anxieties.

Towards the Solution of the “Eastern Embroglio”: Parallel Visions in the Penny Press

In an article published in *The Standard* on 10 June 1876, the newspaper’s Parisian correspondent wrote a review of an article by French journalist Émile de Girardin on how to bring the Eastern Question to its end. According to the reviewer, Girardin proposed to establish an alliance between the Russian Empire, Italy, France, and the German Empire, isolate the British Empire, and sacrifice the Ottoman and Austro-Hungarian Empires.⁴²⁸ The proposed scenario did not

⁴²⁶ “M. Yhiers and the Suez Canal.,” *The Morning Post*, December 22, 1875, 7.

⁴²⁷ Ković, *Disraeli and the Eastern Question*, 171–172.

⁴²⁸ “France.,” *The Standard*, June 10, 1876, 5.

presume a war but instead offered a lasting peace. Yet, the *Standard's* correspondent concluded that Girardin believed in miracles, for which there was no space in political matters.⁴²⁹

The reference to “belief in miracles” is a clear sign of the situational evaluations of the future of the Eastern Question. In one of his seminal essays, Reinhart Koselleck noted that the experiences and expectations of an individual always intertwine the past and the future, with the connection between the two not necessarily being causal even if the prognostic structure is present.⁴³⁰ Thus, when making a prognosis, a person did not rely entirely on their experience, which is especially visible in the modern era when their expectations have become detached from the lived experience and were more closely connected to the belief in progress. To clarify the potential disparities this shift might have caused, Koselleck introduces the notion of the simultaneity of non-simultaneous, which he also applied to the studies of conceptual history⁴³¹. From his point of view, every concept contains the simultaneity of ambiguities, which is also visible in the case of the Eastern Question, as it was shown in the previous section.⁴³²

The very simultaneity of ambiguities also revealed itself in the expectation about the potential solutions that the penny press presented to its readers. In the context of the commercial daily media, expectations depended on the envisioned interests of the audience targeted by the different parts of the newspapers, which is overlooked in the literature dealing with the development of the press in the British Empire. It was particularly visible in the discussions that took place in the part of the newspapers dealing with commerce. The Ottoman Empire was an essential receiver of the foreign investment from the British Empire, and its internal disturbances affected the London stock exchange.⁴³³ Thus, throughout the crisis, the observers of the respective columns were pragmatically interested in a quick “settlement” of the “Eastern drama” that unfolded in the Balkans that would stabilize the situation in the international markets

⁴²⁹ “France.,” *The Standard*, June 10, 1876, 5.

⁴³⁰ Koselleck, “«Space of Experience»,” 262.

⁴³¹ Koselleck, “«Space of Experience»,” 266.

⁴³² See Reinhart Koselleck, ‘Begriffsgeschichte and Social History,’ in *Futures Past*, 87.

⁴³³ See V. Necla Geyikdağı, *Foreign Investment in the Ottoman Empire: International Trade and Relations 1854–1914* (London & New York: I.B. Tauris Publishers, 2011). The Ottoman Empire was also affected by the economic crisis of 1873, which made the foreign investors change their priorities and also affected the agriculture, which was one of the most important sectors of its export economy. See, e.g., G. Conte, “Defining financial reforms in the 19th-century capitalist world-economy: The Ottoman case (1838–1914),” *Capital & Class*, 46, no. 1 (2021): 33–58, <https://doi.org/10.1177/03098168211022222>; Şevket Pamuk, “The Ottoman Empire in the “great depression” of 1873–1896,” *The Journal of Economic History* 44, no. 1 (1984): 107–118.

previously affected by the economic crisis of 1873.⁴³⁴ For them, to solve the Eastern Question generally meant to restore order in the “East,” with the conditions for that being a secondary issue.⁴³⁵

The expectations about the “settlement” were quite unstable, as the contributors to the “Money Market” or similar columns in the penny dailies approached the Eastern Question based on its perceived momentous current stage. In early November 1875, when the uprising in Bosnia was an apparent event, a reviewer of *The Standard* paid attention to the incoming falls of the stock market, connecting them with vague reports around the Eastern Question.⁴³⁶ A few weeks later, the same newspaper published a few optimistic statements regarding the Eastern Question that appeared in the press of the Russian Empire, which led to the strengthening of the stock exchange in London.⁴³⁷ Yet, on 27 November, when the news about the purchase of the shares of the Suez Channel by the British Empire came through, the *Morning Post*’s author argued twice in the ‘Money Market and City News’ column that this very purchase might lead to the difficulties in relations to the Eastern Question.⁴³⁸ The commercial affairs, sensitive to the news flows, thus created a vivid area for the concept familiar for the British reading public to be assessed and interpreted within a different temporality amidst the developing crisis.⁴³⁹

Additionally, the differences in expectations regarding the “settlement” of the question could appear simultaneously on different pages of the same issue. On 20 January 1877, a few days after the failure of the Constantinople Conference, *The Standard* published two articles with opposite views on the situation. On the one hand, the newspaper put the words of the conservative politician Edward Stanhope who told with hope the British Empire would not be involved in the Eastern question⁴⁴⁰. On the other hand, they presented a report from the gathering

⁴³⁴ See, e.g., “Money Market.,” *The Standard*, April 6, 1876, 6; “Money Market.,” *The Daily Telegraph*, October 12, 1876, 2; “Money Market.,” *The Daily Telegraph*, January 20, 1877, 2; “Money Market.,” *The Standard*, March 15, 1877, 6.

⁴³⁵ The ideas about the need to “settle” the Eastern Question appeared in the texts on commercial affairs even amidst the fights of the Russo-Ottoman war. On July 19, 1877, a reviewer of the *Daily News* noted that there was a need “to arrive to a durable settlement of the Eastern Question,” meaning establishing peace in the South-Eastern Europe, although with the involvement of two empires at war (See “Money Market,” *The Daily Telegraph*, July 19, 1877, 2).

⁴³⁶ “Money Market.,” *The Standard*, November 5, 1875, 6.

⁴³⁷ “Money Market.,” *The Standard*, November 23, 1875, 6.

⁴³⁸ “Money Market and City News.,” *The Morning Post*, November 23, 1875, 2.

⁴³⁹ On January 6, 1876, a contributor to the *Standard* paid attention to the “uneasiness” related to the Eastern Question, while a week later, he formed an expectation that the question “may soon be virtually shelved.” (“Money Market.,” *The Standard*, January 10, 1876, 6 and “Money Market.,” *The Standard*, January 17, 1876, 6)

⁴⁴⁰ “Mr. Stanhope, M. P., on Public Affairs.,” *The Standard*, January 20, 1877, 2.

in Exeter, where one of the participants talked about the difficult Eastern Question that Lord Derby, the head of the Foreign Office, had to deal with.⁴⁴¹ Neither of the correspondents talked about the solution themselves, but by publishing their reports the newspaper nevertheless strengthened the atomized character of the Eastern Question.

Hopes to settle the Eastern Question were brought to the public on the eves of each of the international gatherings in 1875-1878. For instance, such hopes appeared before the meeting of the German, Russian, and Austrian plenipotentiaries in Berlin in April-May 1876.⁴⁴² Two years later, they appeared again before the Congress in the very same Berlin.⁴⁴³ As one of *The Standard's* commentators noted, "if the Congress of Berlin settles the Eastern Question both pacifically and satisfactorily, then let no one again ask what is the use of diplomacy"⁴⁴⁴. The possibility of dealing with the Eastern Question was seen as realistic.

To "settle" the Eastern Questions, however, did not mean to "solve" it in a more long-term sense. In the editorial published on 21 June 1878, a few days after the congress was opened, the *Standard* doubted whether "the Eastern Question will be finally settled at the Congress."⁴⁴⁵ The "final settlement," which for different commentators might have meant different things, never appeared as a real possibility in the penny press throughout the crisis. The indefinite vision of the future culminated first in the speech of Lord Derby in December 1875, which was later widely discussed in the press. Commenting on the purchase of the Suez Canal shares, the minister argued that no one foresaw the "final solution of the Eastern Question," and there was no point to open the whole question.⁴⁴⁶ Neither a solution was envisioned, nor any real factors for it to happen were present for those engaging with it at that moment.

Unclear visions of the question's future also marked its undefined temporality during the crisis and beyond it. At the very same moment when Lord Derby commented on the Suez Canal, he also made a remark that "the eternal Eastern question is before us again."⁴⁴⁷ The reference to

⁴⁴¹ "Agriculturists at Exeter," *The Standard*, January 20, 1877, 2.

⁴⁴² See "The Eastern Question," *The Daily Telegraph*, April 24, 1876, 5; "Money Market," *The Standard*, May 12, 1876, 6.

⁴⁴³ "The prospects of peace..." *The Standard*, April 19, 1878, 4; "It is much to be..." *The Standard*, May 9, 1878, 4; "The Suez Canal Company," *The Standard*, June 12, 1878, 5; "The very moment..." *The Standard*, June 12, 1878, 4.

⁴⁴⁴ "Nothing that has yet..." *The Standard*, June 5, 1878, 4.

⁴⁴⁵ "The Congress has now..." *The Standard*, June 21, 1878, 4.

⁴⁴⁶ "The Earl of Derby at Edinburgh," *The Morning Post*, December 20, 1875, 3. The purchase of the shares was also not seen as a part of the solution (see "London, Monday, Dec. 20, 1875," *The Morning Post*, December 3, 1875, 4).

⁴⁴⁷ "Lord Derby at Edinburgh." *The Standard*, December 18, 1875, 3.

the “eternity” of the question was frequently made in the context of the expectations about the potential solutions of the question, especially at the early stages of the crisis.⁴⁴⁸ On 31 August 1875, the Parisian correspondent of the *Standard* underlined that the “eternal and irrepressible Eastern question will be once more staved off.”⁴⁴⁹ Several days later, the observer of the same newspaper summarized that the question “urgently demands to be solved.”⁴⁵⁰ Evidently, the solution was not found. As one noted, “the strength of the Ottoman Empire lies in the mutual embarrassments of those who would profit by its weaknesses.”⁴⁵¹ The presence of the Eastern Question thus was guaranteed by the existing international order in Europe that, while shaken by the series of uprisings and wars on the Balkan peninsula, remained stable for the contributors of the daily press. After the Congress of Berlin was over, the Eastern Question was still seen as irrepressible.⁴⁵²

The visions of the question’s eternity overlapped with contradicting ideas about the presence of the Eastern Question in the past. William Kelley made a good case to conceptualize the Eastern Question as a “historical question” in British intellectual circles of the time.⁴⁵³ The penny press has also provided some space for the discussions about its history, although it did not always utilize it for political purposes. For example, on 26 June 1878, *The Standard* published a review on a collection of conversations with French politicians that promised to tell their readers about the “the French view of the Eastern Question eighteen years ago, when it did not materially differ from what it was only three years ago.”⁴⁵⁴ The book referred to the times after the Crimean War, a memory which was also a point of reference for a few observers.⁴⁵⁵ Therefore, these were the lived experiences of the present and memory, often still

⁴⁴⁸ It was Karl Marx who is considered to be the first to use the metaphor “the eternal Eastern Question” in one of his letters to Fridrich Engels during the Crimean War (See Karl Marx, “Turkey.” In *The Eastern Question: A Reprint of Letters written 1853-1856 dealing with the Events of the Crimean War*, ed. Eleanor Marx Aveling and Edward Aveling (London: Swan Sonnenschein & Co. Ltd., 1897), 2).

⁴⁴⁹ “France.” *The Standard* August 31, 1875, 5.

⁴⁵⁰ “The announcement made by...” *The Standard*, September 3, 1875, 4.

⁴⁵¹ “Any rumour about...” *The Daily Telegraph*, January 10, 1878, 4.

⁴⁵² See “Sir Michael Hicks Beach and Lord Elcho in Gloucestershire.” *The Standard*, September 21, 1878, 2 and a similar note at “Sir Michael Hicks-Beach, M. P., at Winchcombe.” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 21, 1878, 3.

⁴⁵³ See Kelley, “Intellectuals and the Eastern Question.”

⁴⁵⁴ “Seniors «Conversations».” *The Standard*, June 26, 1878, 2.

⁴⁵⁵ “The speech of Mr. Bright...” *The Standard*, January 4, 1877, 4; “An Imperial signif anc ,” *h D ly Telegraph*, December 4, 1877, 4.

communicative, about the lived experiences of the past that defined the Eastern Question's temporality.⁴⁵⁶

Contrary to the reflections on “eternity,” the roots of the Eastern Question did not preoccupy the contributors to the penny press, and the reflections on that originated mostly from different cited passages published on their pages. On 12 April 1878, *The Standard* quoted the words of the conservative politician George Hamilton who mentioned it as “chronic difficulty for the last fifty years.”⁴⁵⁷ An observer of the *Daily Telegraph* went further in a review on a pamphlet by the Russian general Rostislav Fadeeff, starting his account about the Eastern Question from 1807, the year of the treaty of Tilsit.⁴⁵⁸ The very same treaty appeared in the book of Henry Rawlinson, reviewed in the daily press during the crisis.⁴⁵⁹ Liberal MP Henry James, cited by a few dailies, pointed out that the Eastern Question has been in focus since 1791, when Edmund Burke openly questioned the bad governance and corruption in the Ottoman Empire.⁴⁶⁰ James also referred to the Crimean war among other moments that highlighted the continuity of the question rather than its beginning, thus combining both an event that was still a part of communicative memory of his circles with more distanced cultural memory powered by historical accounts.⁴⁶¹

However, it was the advertisement that went the furthest in marking the age of the unsolved Eastern Question. In mid-1877, a few newspapers published a small piece informing about the work *Key to the Eastern Question*, which offered a number of “[h]istorical Notes on Poland (sic!), Turkey, and Russia, from the year 1650 to the present time.”⁴⁶² Going back to the contestations between the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, the Ottoman Empire, and Moscow in the mid-seventeenth century, the author thus caught the attention of the readers with the omnipresent concept that did not necessary had to deal with the historical context of the

⁴⁵⁶ On communicative , s an sm “Communicative and Cultural Memory,” in *Cultural hi l int of View*, ed. Peter Meusburger, Michael Heffernan, pringer, 2011), 15-27.

⁴⁵⁷ “Middlesex Election,” *The Sta ar A i l* , he e r ce to 50 years of the Eastern Question's history als e Standard published in the end of August 1878 (see “The Impending Impeach ment,” *The Standard*, August 26, 1878, 5).

⁴⁵⁸ “Russia's Real Policy,” *The Daily Telegraph*, October 26, 1876, 3.

⁴⁵⁹ See. Henry Rawlinson, *England and Russia in the East. A Series of Papers on the Political and Geographical Condition of Central Asia* (London: J. Murray, 1875), 18.

⁴⁶⁰ “Sir Henry James on the Eastern Question,” *The Daily Telegraph*, May 23, 1877, 3 and “Sir Henry James at Hereford,” *The Standard*, May 23, 1877, 3.

⁴⁶¹ Henry James was born in 1828.

⁴⁶² “Key to the Eastern Question,” *The Daily Telegraph*, June 7, 1877, 2; “Key to the Eastern Question...,” *The Standard*, June 7, 1877, 8.

book, which served one of the starting points of the contemporary crisis without a clear sign of any possible solutions. The solution was offered in another piece, advertised in London dailies. In February 1878, the readers were encouraged to read the title *The “Last Days” and Things Coming upon the Earth: or, the Eastern Question and the War in the Light of Scripture Prophecy*.⁴⁶³ It was put between a short ad of the biography of Pope Pius IX who died on February 7 and a book on investment. A copy of the “Last Days” cost six pennies, which equaled the price of six apples on London streets, and was certainly targeting the mass audience interested in curiosities.⁴⁶⁴ For an ordinary reader in Victorian Britain, this book might have been more valuable than the reflections on the solutions to the Eastern Question in other parts of the newspaper, as the ubiquitous doubt about the very possibility of the solution marked the pages of the daily press.⁴⁶⁵

Conclusion

The Eastern Question appeared as a mosaic and often atomized concept in the Victorian daily press during the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875-1878. Although the new controversies in the Balkans started in summer 1875, the newspaper authors had not connected them regularly with the Eastern Question until the mid-autumn of the same year. Introducing the column “The Eastern Question” in *The Daily Telegraph* was the only precise attempt to interpret the events in the Balkans through the lens of the question. At the same time, the authors of the column did not explain the meanings of the concept, presuming that the readers were familiar with them. The interpretations of the situation could change quickly, which led to multiple mentions about reopening of the Eastern Question and the presence of opposing views during 1875 and after and also resulted in the gradual inclusion of its disparate geographies.

⁴⁶³ “The «Last Days» and Things Coming upon the Earth...,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 8; “The «Last Days» and Things Coming upon the Earth...,” *The Daily Telegraph*. February 19, 1878, 4.

⁴⁶⁴ Irving Fang points out that the cheap newspapers had to compete with the buns and apples sellers to attract a customer on the streets of London, where the issues were distributed by newspaper boys (Irving Fang, *A History of Mass Communication: Six Information Revolutions* (London & New York: Routledge, 2016), 51–52).

⁴⁶⁵ On February 14, 1878, when the piece of advertisement was published, the *Standard’s* issue had three more articles featuring the Eastern Question, one dealing with the Eastern Crisis, and one – with Eastern affairs. These offered visions on the “crisis in Eastern affairs,” and “difficulties in the Eastern Question,” with only hopes “for peaceful solution” being expressed (see “Although up to yesterday...,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 4; “We are in a pos .,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 4; “The Eastern Crisis.,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 5; “Various idle rumours...,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 6; “G. Hamilton, M.P., on the Crisis.,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 6).

The form of opinions could also be different. There were at least 19 synonyms that replaced the original formulation of ‘the Eastern Question’ on the pages of the daily press, some of which were used to make the texts sound more sensational, nearly always negatively. The newspaper authors referred to the discourse of sensationalism to keep the readers’ attention to the events in the East, and the concept of the Eastern Question in its variation appeared as a useful tool for these purposes.

At the same time, the meanings of the concept were not homogeneous. The authors could refer to several Eastern questions simultaneously, emphasizing either factual or spatial dimensions of the concept. The interpretations were unstable, and sometimes the texts referred to new phases of the Eastern Question that either brought new understandings of the concept or added new connotations to the existing meanings. The concept was temporalized and varied under the influence of external factors or even personal authors' intentions during the whole crisis. The appearance of the ‘party question’ as a new interpretation of the Eastern Question during the Bulgarian agitation in autumn 1876 was one of the most important signs of this variability. The editors who used the phrase in their headlines dealing with British internal politics contributed to the domestication of the concept that previously belonged almost exclusively to the domain of international relations.

With constantly changing forms and different approaches to placement, the visions on the solution of the Eastern Question also appeared in the penny press on different levels. While for the authors of the parts dealing with the commercial affairs it was a short-term “settlement” of the question that mattered the most, the reviewers of other parts offered more long-term visions on the “solution” of the question. With this simultaneous disbalance of visions, the former were the ones who were more optimistic in the long-term, while the latter almost never expressed their confidence in the solution coming soon during the Great Eastern Crisis. Their anxieties and frustrations led to the notions of the “eternity” of the Eastern Question, which was also historicized, both in main parts of the newspapers and the sections presenting the advertisement. Undefined politically, the concept was commodified and thus further domesticated by the means of daily penny press.

Despite its ambiguous character and the presence of multiple meanings, the Eastern Question was a part of everyday life in Victorian Britain during the Great Eastern Crisis, and it was the crisis that made such a presence possible. Its appearance was not limited to the

newspaper articles or speeches delivered by prominent politicians. In the end of February and in the beginning of March 1877, traditional greyhound racing took place at Ashdown Forest in South-Eastern England. After several rounds, the Irish greyhound, Eastern Question, confidently won the race.⁴⁶⁶

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⁴⁶⁶ “Ashdown Meeting.” *The Standard*, March 1, 1877, 6; “Coursing.” *The Standard*, March 2, 1877, 6; “Coursing.” *The Standard*, March 3, 1877, 6. The newspaper correspondent reported that the greyhound British Queen was a runner-up of the race.

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Figures

Figure 1. The Mentions of the ‘Eastern Question’ in *The Daily Telegraph*, 1875-1878

Figure 2. The Mentions of the 'Eastern Question' in *The Standard*, 1875-1878

Figure 3. The Mentions of the 'Eastern Question' in *The Daily News*, 1875-1878

Figure 4. The Mentions of the 'Eastern Question' in *The Manchester Guardian*, 1875-1878

Figure 5. The column "The Eastern Question" in *The Daily Telegraph*, 1875-1878